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Perceptions of European Societies

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1. Introduction

The objective of this report is to investigate media narratives on perceptions of borders and how these relate to the wider European Union project, and current political processes in minority regions in Europe. Specifically, we seek to identify border narratives in a selection of minority language newspapers across a comparative case study of five European contexts, in Czechia, Denmark, Germany, Italy, and Slovakia. The aim is to investigate the possible role of key de- and re-bordering events, including the 2015 humanitarian crisis and the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, in shaping perceptions of borders and the European project in minority regions. We focus on recent re-bordering trends in Europe, as they are seen to present a threat to the process of European integration and are likely to alter perceptions of European heritage, including shared values, beliefs, and traditions. The analysis presented in the study unpacks the significance of border narratives during times of perceived crisis. We are also interested in how a vision of Europe is shared and expressed by media outlets in these specific regional minority contexts and consider what the findings of this report may signify for the future of the European project.

The report is structured in the following way. First, we set out our justification for the study and provide an overview of the extant literature relating to border narratives in minority regions. Next, we give a summary of the methodology followed in the study, including the coding-scheme followed, which was structured in a manner to provide consistent and comparable results across the case studies. We then present the four-case study reports, one from each region, before reflecting on the findings in the discussion section. The report concludes with a concise summary of the main results of the study and the comparisons that can be drawn between the case study regions. This leads us to return to the key research questions posed at the outset of the study and list the contributions that we have made. The report responds to the following key research questions:

- How are borders presented in minority newspaper media?
- Which narratives are used in the reporting on borders?
- How do minority newspapers frame the EU within reporting on borders?

2. Conceptual Background and Study Rationale

This research has been undertaken as part of the Horizon Europe B-Shapes project¹, which explores how borders shape peoples' perceptions of Europe and the European project. In this research national minorities were explicitly chosen to cover societal groups that have rarely been researched in depth in the context of border narratives and narratives of Europe. A concise definition of national minorities is difficult to identify in the literature from minority studies. For this study, we use a rather broad definition provided by Ringelheim:

“As well known, there is currently no legally binding definition of the ‘minority’ in international law. However, it has been traditionally accepted that a minority is a group which is smaller in number than the rest of the population and whose members fulfil at least two conditions: they have ethnical, religious, or linguistic features different from those of the majority, and are animated by the will to preserve these distinctive characteristics.” (Ringelheim, 2010, p.10)

For our study, which focuses on national minorities, we use this definition, but we are aware of the problematic issues with such explanations and understand that each state has its own approach because, as mentioned above, there is no international binding definition of a minority.

National minorities have a complex relationship with borders. For national minorities, borders can symbolise their multiple functions, including how they act as instruments of power, identity markers, and providing opportunities for cooperation. States often create, impose, and reinforce borders through arbitrary, coercive, and violent processes in response to political, socio-economic, and security concerns. The asymmetrical power relations of states and minorities can lead to the marginalisation of minorities in political, socio-cultural, historiographical, and economic terms, with borders and (re-)bordering policies causing tense relations between what the border, as a powerful reminder of past injustices, means for the minorities and what it symbolises in nation-state narratives. Research has shown that European citizens are made to feel that they are living in a constant threat of border crisis due to the impact of political rhetoric and news concentration on the issue (Vaughan-Williams, 2021). Citizens are made to feel that borders provide greater security, while also being dependent on increased security measures to keep the population safe from external threats. It has also been argued that border narratives simultaneously provide security and provoke insecurity among the general population in European states. These narratives are of relevance during so-called crisis moments.

In recent years we have seen a re-affirmation of political borders, during crisis events. These include the 2015 humanitarian crisis, and the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. The concept of border-fencing refers to the “systematic closure of national borders across the world”, as we have witnessed in the last decade, such as during the pandemic (“Covid-fencing”, Medeiros et al., 2020) or during other events (e.g. migration-fencing). In these critical moments we can observe how political, symbolic, and cultural boundaries have become more visible, particularly in border regions. This dynamic process also emphasises the in-

¹ The B-Shapes website can be found at: <https://www.sdu.dk/en/forskning/forskningsenheder/samf/b-shapes>

betweenness of national minorities, who are situated in complex multi-level interactions and reaffirms the special role that borders have for minority communities, both as historical legacy and as part of everyday lives and familiar landscapes (Balogh & Pete, 2018; Böhm, 2019; Tarvet & Klatt, 2023).

Recent scholarship has underlined the importance of the media in conveying and constructing narratives and political discourse on borders. Our research draws on the narrative approach in border studies (Opilowska, 2021). Narratives can be thought of as stories which people may choose to align with or, conversely, to distance themselves from (White, 1990). Plummer (2019) has emphasised the ability of narratives to simultaneously foster feelings of belonging, and feelings of exclusion within population groups. News media, including print media, plays an important role in perpetuating border narratives through discourse and storytelling. Narratives are a discursive strategy deployed to interpret and understand the political realities of the world around us (Budabin and Richey, 2021, p. 228) and can be used to shape public opinion. Stories are created and shared among audiences to persuade and guide people on political issues. Narratives are therefore not neutral, but shape and are shaped by, political acts.

Previous research has emphasised the significant role of the media in framing news stories during moments of crisis in a specific manner which can guide public opinion. For example, in relation to the so - termed migration crisis, and other immigration related issues (Rodríguez-Pérez et al., 2022). News media reporting on immigration issues also highlights the perceived threat that migrants are seen to present, or the potential economic impact (Dekker and Scholten, 2017). More recently, scholars have also turned their attention to the study of social media platforms to examine how border narratives are constructed and shared by migration governance actors (Brandle and Tolochko, 2023). These narrative framings are also applicable in the study of borders more broadly.

In this report we employ a narrative approach (Czarniawska, 2010; Esin et al., 2014; Andrews et al., 2013) to explore how borders, heritage and Europe are understood, framed, and interpreted by newspapers with a special focus on minorities. In this sense we focus on public narratives in minority newspapers of borders which contributes to shaping their perceptions of Europe, these local narratives trace the special significance of the border and its historical past, border closures in the context of crises. The narrative approach is closely aligned to studies of discourse.² This report focuses on specific media narratives and not on discourse in the general sense as our primary objective is to understand border narratives across the case study regions. However, we acknowledge the close links between narrative and discourse, and understand the two as interconnected processes, not separate fields of study.

² For further detail on the narrative approach adopted in B-Shapes please see Deliverable 2.1: Study report on borders as factors shaping borderlanders' perceptions of Europe and the European project.

3. Methodology

The methodology applied in this study is a thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006) of newspaper articles, which is used to investigate media presentations of borders and Europe and make comparisons between minority media outlets across the case study country selection. To carry out our analysis we first identified appropriate newspapers, selected a suitable timeframe for analysis, and developed a common coding scheme to be applied in the minority newspapers' reporting across our select case studies. The newspapers were selected according to the readership numbers (preference for those media outlets with a comparatively high reach within the minority community), the year of establishment (preference for newspapers with a longer establishment) and the focus on the local borderland.

Table 1: Overview on the minority communities and the analysed newspapers

Minority	Settlement area and size ³	Newspaper	
German minority in Denmark	North Schleswig Estimated 12,000-15,000	Der Nordschleswiger	Language: German Daily paper until 2021 Since 2021 online medium with a bi-weekly printed version
Danish minority in Germany	South Schleswig Estimated 50,000	Flensburg Avis	Language: Danish Published six days a week
German-speaking minority in Italy	Autonomous Province of Bolzano/Bozen (South Tyrol) 314,604 according to 2011 census	Dolomiten	Language: German Published six days a week
Polish minority in Czechia	Predominantly in Zaolzie region (Těšínské Slezsko) Estimated 20,000-40,000	Głos	Language: Polish Published twice a week and online medium
Hungarian minority in Slovakia	Predominantly in southern Slovakia; in the census of 2021, 422,065 declared Hungarian ethnicity and 462,165 Hungarian as native language	Új Szó	Language: Hungarian Print and online newspaper
		Felvidék.ma	Language: Hungarian Online news portal

To decide the timeframe for the analysis, we followed the B-Shapes methodological approach to reconstruct narratives punctuated by “meaningful events” (see B-Shapes Deliverable 2.1, 2023, p. 8) and focused on the increasing migration flows in 2015 and 2016 and the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic in 2020 as key moments for our analysis. These two moments can be described as critical moments in recent history, which brought about large-scale processes of re-bordering across Europe, and provoked public debate surrounding borders and border politics. It was left to research teams to decide on the specific months to focus on in their analysis, but for consistency all case studies deal with these two periods.

³ Numbers are based on available estimations or census data.

As WP4 primarily seeks to investigate narratives related to the state border, newspaper articles were selected by filtering with the keywords “border/bordering” (in the respective languages of the case study regions). To include other relevant articles that do not mention the words “border/bordering”, the titles of the remaining articles were read and, if deemed relevant, included. A total of 1285 newspaper articles were coded in the research for this study.

Table 2: Coded articles per newspaper

Newspaper	Number of articles coded
Der Nordschleswiger	623
Flensburg Avis	311
Dolomiten	454
Új Szó Felvidék.ma	150
Głos	167

To conduct our analysis, we developed a common coding scheme for all minority newspapers by applying a mixed deductive and inductive approach. We consulted the data and earlier conceptual reports of the B-Shapes project⁴ to develop the following general coding frame:

- general information on the article (e.g. type of article, position within the newspaper, headline)
- general information on the border/s that is/are treated in the article (e.g. state border local to the newspaper, state borders in general, Schengen borders)
- narratives on the border (e.g. border as bridge, border as fence, border as identity shaper)
- narratives on Europe (e.g. crisis in/of Europe, fortress Europe, humanitarian Europe)
- actors who carry the narratives (e.g. politicians, economic actors, civil society distinguished by supposed gender and majority/minority affiliation)

The coding scheme was first tested on a limited set of data in each of the case study regions. After this pilot study, the coding scheme was adapted and revised, and finally used for the analysis of all data in each of the case study regions. To ensure that the study also considers, and analyses specific local realities and themes related to the minority contexts of the different case studies, the coding scheme allows for general codes to be complemented by sub-codes which are created inductively based on the data analysed in each case study region. It should be noted, however, that coding does not provide us with all the nuances of less reported codes, and this is a small limitation in the methodology. Nevertheless, coding frameworks are particularly valuable in comparative case studies using thematic analysis (Nowell et al. 2017). Following this method, we sought to compile a general picture of borderland reporting in these minority media outlets.

⁴ The conceptual approach adopted in the B-Shapes project is further elaborated in report Deliverable 2.1: Study report on borders as factors shaping borderlanders’ perceptions of Europe and the European project.

With the thematic analysis approach of the study, we were able to identify the co-occurrence of concepts and patterns within the data to pick out the key border narratives and make comparisons between the country data sets. Braun and Clarke (2006) note six key phases of a successful thematic analysis: familiarization with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining, and naming themes, and producing the final report. Following this guide as a template, we first identified the main themes in the articles, which were used to generate initial codes in our codebook. We then reported on the frequency of the initial codes and their co-occurrence (quantitative analysis). In the next step we identified relationships between the themes and the codes, in relation to the larger border narratives identified in the B-Shapes Report D2.1, and grouped these under these categorisations. For example, common narrative categorisations included: border as fence, border as security device, border as bridge, crisis Europe etc. We then explored who were the actors telling the border narratives. For example, if the narrators were minority politicians, citizens, or representatives of the kin state. This helped us to make connections between the narratives that were shared and the actors who participate in their production and dissemination.

In our comparison of the case studies, we were able to contrast patterns in the data analysed in the case study regions and make generalisations about the results gathered in the study. This is elaborated in the discussion and conclusion sections of this report. Additionally, we can make broader claims about the differences between the two time periods studied, and how border narratives differed across these. Through the carefully organised thematic analysis, we arrive at several key conclusions about the substance and construction of border narratives that are told in national minority newspaper reporting. The first case study region we approach in this report is that of South Tyrol, Italy.

4. Case Study Reports

4.1. The ‘Dolomiten’ in the Italian-Austrian Borderland

Authors: Alice Engl, Johanna Mitterhofer & Marcus Nicolson

4.1.1 Background Information

The Autonomous Province of Bolzano/Bozen, also known as South Tyrol, is located in northern Italy, on the Austrian and Swiss borders. Its population of approximately 516,000 is composed of 70% German-speakers, 26% Italian-speakers and 4.5% Ladin-speakers. The large percentage of German-speakers is the result of a redrawing of borders after the First World War, when South Tyrol, until then part of the Habsburg Empire, became part of Italy. After significant social and political tensions, in 1972 South Tyrol received the Second Statute of Autonomy, a complex power-sharing system through which the German-speaking population in South Tyrol enjoys one of the world’s most advanced systems of minority protection. Critics of the autonomy system point out, however, that because of rigid institutional separation between the three linguistic groups with, among other aspects, separate educational institutions, it has contributed to reinforcing divisions between the groups. Unresolved issues around contested Fascist heritage contribute to ongoing disputes between majority and minority representatives in the region. Socio-cultural, political, and economic ties between the German-speaking minority in South Tyrol and the Austrian Land Tyrol are strong, and together with the Trentino, South Tyrol, and Tyrol, form an integrated border area through the cross-border region “Euregio Tyrol-South Tyrol-Trentino”.

There are currently four daily newspapers in South Tyrol (Dolomiten, Die Neue Südtiroler Tageszeitung, Alto Adige, Salto). We selected ‘Dolomiten’ for the media analysis as it is the oldest and most widely read newspaper in South Tyrol and the local newspaper with the highest circulation in Italy (Gross/Schönthaler 2024), reaching a total of 210,000 daily readers (Athesia Medien, 2023). It therefore has a dominant position in opinion-forming processes in South Tyrol. Founded in 1923, ‘Dolomiten’ is published by South Tyrol’s most prominent publishing house Athesia and is produced in print six days a week with 46,000 daily copies consisting of 42 pages. Since 2002, ‘Dolomiten’ is also available digitally. ‘Dolomiten’'s chief editor Toni Ebner is closely embedded in the South Tyrolean economy and politics, with close connections to the SVP political party.

Articles from two key moments of rebordering were selected for the analysis: February-July 2016 and March-August 2020. In February 2016, the Austrian government announced the decision to erect a fence at the Brenner border to manage migration flows. By July 2016, this decision was renounced. In March 2020, borders were closed in response to the Covid-outbreak and were then re-opened in August of the same year. All articles from these months were then further screened for analysis by selecting only those containing the words “Grenz*” [border] and the two local border crossings of Brenner and Winnebach. Based on this screening, a total of 454 articles were coded (351 for 2016, 103 for 2020).

Table 3: Articles coded for the ‘Dolomiten’ newspaper

Month	Number of articles coded	Month	Number of articles coded
February 2016	114	March 2020	20
March 2016	64	April 2020	12
April 2016	87	May 2020	25
May 2016	65	June 2020	25
June 2016	10	July 2020	9
July 2016	11	August 2020	12

4.1.2 Narratives on Borders and Europe

The border appeared as a central concept in media reporting during the period February – May 2016. In these months, the concept of the border frequently appeared in prominent positions in both headlines and on the title pages.

Table 4: Keyword “border” featuring on title pages and in article headlines in the ‘Dolomiten’ newspaper

	title page_yes	headline_yes	Total number of coded articles
2016_02	13	75	114
2016_03	5	33	64
2016_04	9	58	87
2016_05	5	41	65
2016_06	0	6	10
2016_07	0	5	11
2020_03	0	9	20
2020_04	0	4	12
2020_05	3	20	25
2020_06	0	21	25
2020_07	0	4	9
2020_08	0	6	12

Additionally, the key word “fence” is associated to the concept of border and enters the narrative as exemplified by the following selection of headlines:

- “A fence on the Brenner would have terrible symbolic power” (11/02/2016)
- “A fence would be the "end of the European region of Tyrol" (06/02/2016a)
- “Fences are an expression of the weakness of politics” (12/02/2016)

During the second period considered in the media analysis, the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, the concept of the border was particularly prevalent in May-June 2020 with comparatively more border-related headlines than in the other months analysed for 2020, and a number of articles calling for border-(re)opening:

- “Border closures are „borderline” (19/05/2020)
- “Immediate opening of the Brenner Pass demanded” (30/05/2020)

Analysis of the frequency of codes shows that overall, the concept of “border” was less present during the Covid crisis than during the so-termed “migration crisis” in 2016. As such, it appears that increased migration, and the discussion of these issues in the media, has had a greater effect on how the border is narrated. Main findings are listed as follows:

- The most dominant code in the analysis was “border as a fence” with its child codes “fence as threat”, “fence as immunity tool” and “fence as security device”. With 392 references in 2016 and 122 references in 2020, it indicates a focus on physical barriers and security measures related to the migration crisis and the pandemic. Subcodes related to the proposed border fence as a threat were particularly prominent in the early months of 2016. In 2020 discourses around the fence as an immunity tool emerged.
- The second most present code was “crisis Europe”, with 137 references in 2016 and 28 references in 2020. This includes both crisis *in* Europe (i.e. a crisis provoked by the outside) and crisis *of* Europe (i.e. a condition caused by Europe itself), indicating a perception of a Europe that is under threat both from within and outside.
- The code of the border as a 'site of transgression' was applied 111 times, referring to reports of irregular border crossings, protests, and acts of civil disobedience at the border, with most reports from 2016.
- Codes of “fortress Europe/gated Europe” were applied 67 times, pointing to narratives of the importance of Europe’s external borders.
- 'Identity shaper' appeared 57 times in the coded articles, signalling the salience of the border's influence on local minority identities.
- 'Border as bridge' was referenced 55 times, highlighting the symbolic role of borders as connectors and the cross-border integrated area.
- 'Othering' was referenced 54 times, suggesting narratives that create divisions or distinctions between social groups, particularly between the local population and migrants.
- The least frequent code was “open/humanitarian Europe”, representing narratives emphasizing humanitarian efforts or values in relation to providing support to migrants. As will be shown later, discussions that emphasize humanitarian aspects or values are indeed nearly absent in the ‘*Dolomiten*’ border narratives.
- In terms of the type of border mentioned in the articles, the local state border – that is, the Austrian-Italian border between South Tyrol and Austrian Tyrol – dominated in the newspapers examined (590 references), followed by borders of other states (77), particularly in Austria, the

borders of the EU/Schengen in general (57), while Italian state borders beyond those located in South Tyrol were only mentioned 5 times.

Table 5: Frequency of codes regarding the main narratives on borders and Europe in the ‘Dolomiten’ newspaper

	Dolomiten 2016	Dolomiten 2020	Total
border as fence (incl. child codes fence as threat, fence as security device, fence as immunity device)	392	122	514
crisis Europe	137	28	165
border as site of transgression	59	5	64
border as bridge	66	26	92
gated Europe_fortress Europe	64	3	67
border opening_de-bordering	29	32	61
border as identity shaper	51	6	57
border as othering	49	5	54
open_humanitarian Europe	39	1	40

Figure 1: Most common codes for narratives in 2016 in the ‘Dolomiten’ newspaper

Figure 2: Most common codes for narratives in 2020 in the ‘Dolomiten’ newspaper

The narratives have a spatial dimension that presents the Brenner pass as a distinctive place. The media reporting emphasizes the Brenner border as “not just any border” (07/05/2016) but as a “special symbol of European integration” (22/02/2016a). The ‘Dolomiten’ newspaper cites both political representatives of the German-speaking minority in South Tyrol and political actors outside this community with statements regarding this special symbolical role. Example headlines include: “*The Brenner Pass is not just any border in Europe, it symbolises what the European states have achieved together*” (Herbert Dorfmann, South Tyrol’s MEP,⁵ 25/02/2016a), “*closing the Brenner border [...] would be a cut into the heart of Schengen*” (Donald Tusk, EU Council President 23/04/2016), „*The closure of the Brenner Pass, a symbol of European integration, [...] would be a stab in the heart of the European Union*“ (Matteo Renzi, Italian Prime Minister, 23/02/2016a). Often these statements have a very emotional tone (such as the reference to cutting or stabbing at Europe’s heart).

Types of narrators and narratives

Narratives were produced primarily by politicians, particularly from the German-speaking minority and politicians from Austria, the minority’s kin state, followed by economic actors, providing a highly political and often politicised frame to the narratives. Civil society actors and civil servants were much less common while other categories of narrators were absent, as the following table shows:

⁵ The functions / titles of the narrators cited apply to the time the coded articles were written (2016 or 2020).

Table 6: Intersections between coded types of narrators and most frequent narratives in the ‘Dolomiten’

	politicians	economic actors	civil society	civil servants	experts	inhabitants	migrants
border as bridge	61	6	8	0	3	4	0
border fence as a threat	146	50	20	3	1	3	0
threat to minority identity	36	0	6	0	0	0	0
threat to economy	13	16	4	0	0	0	0
other/ general threat	23	2	0	1	0	0	0
threat to migrants	3	0	11	0	0	0	0
border fence as security device	120	3	5	18	0	0	0
border fence as immunity tool	26	2	1	1	1	0	0
border as identity shaper	47	0	3	1	2	2	0
border as othering	34	0	7	4	0	2	1
border as site of transgression	24	3	3	10	0	0	0
border opening_debordering	37	3	5	3	6	1	0
crisis Europe	134	11	12	2	5	0	0
gated Europe_fortress Europe	57	4	2	1	0	0	0
open_humanitarian Europe	13	1	17	1	0	0	0
TOTAL	699	83	83	44	18	12	1

As evidenced in the table below, minority actors were overall the most common category of narrators, followed closely by kin state actors. Narrators from the Italian-speaking population of South Tyrol, the national Italian context, or the EU were much less common. One key determinant of “who speaks” is the ‘Dolomiten’'s position as *the* voice of the minority, and its reliance on reprints of German and Austrian Press agency articles leading to an overrepresentation of Austrian (kin state) and an underrepresentation of national Italian narratives. It also points to the distribution of visibility and power in South Tyrol, the historical importance of kin state relations, the persistence of the idea of a common cross-border identity, and a perceived and actual distance of the nation-state of Italy.

Table 7: Coding intersections between community-type of narrators and narratives in the ‘Dolomiten’

	minority	Kin state	national	majority	EU
border as bridge	42	14	6	11	2
border fence as a threat	136	34	25	9	7
threat to minority identity	30	9	1	1	1
threat to economy	28	3	1	0	1
other or general threat	18	2	2	2	1
fence as threat to migrants	6	1	1	3	3
border fence as immunity tool	7	14	2	0	5
border fence as security device	28	80	17	4	5
border as identity shaper	25	14	5	4	1
border as othering	13	23	7	1	1
border as site of transgression	14	16	4	2	0
border opening_de-bordering	18	15	6	2	3
crisis Europe	61	36	28	6	17
gated Europe_fortress Europe	15	26	8	3	4
open_humanitarian Europe	13	6	7	3	2
TOTAL	329	205	85	28	44

We also observe a large gender disparity among the actors that are cited in the newspaper. 87% of coded narrators are male, whereas only 13% are female. This disparity applies to all categories of coded narrators.

Figure 3: Gender distribution of coded narrators in the ‘Dolomiten’

A correlation can be established between narratives and narrators: minority politicians predominantly talk about the border as a bridge that connects the minority to its kin across the border in the Austrian Tyrol, be this culturally, economically, socially, or politically. Narratives on re-bordering are hence constructed around the idea of fences as a threat to cross-border unity. This extends also to narratives on Europe, which are mainly framed in terms of bordering processes as threats to the European project. Kin state politicians, on the other hand, focused on narrations of borders as security or immunity devices to protect the nation state, with little focus on transnational relations and their importance for the kin minority in South Tyrol. The newspaper articles analysed also associated borders with the idea of a Europe in crisis.

Economic actors, the second-most present group of narrators, mainly produced narratives that looked at borders as actual or potential threats to the free movement of services and goods, pointing out the financial consequences of border closures and the associated traffic jams for trucks and the impact of cancellations by tourists on the local tourism trade.

The ‘Dolomiten’ newspaper frames both migration and Covid as threats to the wider European project, but with a much stronger focus on migration. The frequency of reports that connect migration with a crisis in or of Europe (codes “migration” & “crisis Europe” 2016: 137; codes “Covid” & “crisis Europe” 2020: 28) and the use of certain words and images to frame migration (such as refugee stream, refugee problem, mass influx, onslaught of refugees, streams of people, uncontrolled influx) contribute to a narration of migration as a threat.

Narrative of borders as threat to (local) economy, to minority identity and to cross-border relations

This section explores the first key narrative, coded as “border as fence” to refer to those instances where the border was presented as a bordering device that separates and divides, but also protects and controls. Per se a neutral expression, our analysis shows that the codes of “border as fence” were mainly associated with a more negative interpretation of the “fence as a threat” to the economy and to minority identity and culture. This was followed by narratives of the fence as security devices and, in the Covid period, the fence as an immunity tool.

The narrative of the fence as a threat is frequently presented through its negative impacts on the local economy, in particular tourism and the transport of goods over the Brennerpass. Set primarily in the context of the looming threat of the reintroduction of border controls at the Brenner pass in 2016 but also during the Covid-period in 2020, economic as well as minority political actors highlighted the potentially “catastrophic consequences” of border closures for the South Tyrolean economy (Manfred Pinzger, president of South Tyrol’s Association for the Hotel Industry HGV, 06/02/2016b).

Similar superlatives were used in narratives associated with the effects of borders on the minority and its pan-Tyrolean identity, particularly by representatives of the minorities’ right-wing parties: “very bad news” [Hiobsbotschaft]”, “a stab into the heart of the Tyroleans” (Pius Leitner, Die Freiheitlichen, 09/02/2016), a “repeated tearing apart of the Tyrolean “Heimat” (Lois Taibon, Die Freiheitlichen,

18/02/2016). The narratives included references to South Tyrol's difficult past and how these difficulties were overcome thanks to the opening of state borders, and presented the 2016 rebordering processes as setbacks or failures: *"If a fence really were to be erected at the Brenner border, we South Tyroleans would be thrown back into the 1990s... This would be totally backward development for the close connection to Tyrol and the fatherland Austria"* (Stefan Premstaller, SVP, 15/02/2016). These narratives of threat and of regression concerned not only South Tyrol itself, but also the cross-border territory, the EGTC Euroregion Tyrol-South Tyrol-Trentino and, ultimately, the Europe of regions. Moreover, the narratives of "fences as a threat" are employed as emotional appeals to the local population ("I hope that the crisis unites the Tyrolean population even more", Peter Brunner, SVP, mayor of Brixen, 23/02/2016b), to local politics (*"we must continue all our efforts to avoid a border politics that causes suffering the Euroregion Tyrol"* (Philipp Achammer, SVP, 23/02/2016c), and expressions of "disappointment" with the kin state (*"Austria must re-think its plans"*, Helmuth Renzler, SVP, 20/02/2016) who in turn highlight sentiments of "regret" and call for understanding by South Tyrol: *"The decision of opening or closing the borders was not an easy one," says Federal Chancellor Sebastian Kurz, appealing for understanding. And despite the current disgruntlement, Austria continues to have "particularly close ties with South Tyrol"* (Sebastian Kurz, Austrian foreign minister, 11/06/2020).

While South Tyrolean narrators thus portray re-bordering as a threat, kin state narrators (predominantly Austrian politicians) focus on borders as a security device that protects the Austrian state against the influx of external threats. Responsibility for rebordering was frequently delegated: if Brussels or Rome had done what they were supposed to, Vienna would not have needed to re-border the Brenner Pass: *"If everyone closes their borders, we cannot simply stand back and watch how thousands of refugees enter Tyrol daily... That's why we need to use all our diplomatic relations and efforts to put pressure on Rome"* (Günther Platter, president of Tyrol, 08/02/2016). In these narratives, the border was portrayed as a necessary evil.

While narratives on borders abounded during the summer of migrations 2016, accounts of border closures in 2020 coded as "fence as immunity tool" were mainly factual statements devoid of emotions (42 out of 327 coded articles (23%) from the Covid-period) that cannot be defined as narratives according to the definition used in this project. The articles focused on dates and locations (when and which borders closed/reopened) as well as regulations (who can cross the border under which conditions), with little to no critical assessment, additional reporting, or symbolisms. The absence of true narratives as well as the relatively high proportion of narrators from outside South Tyrol, particularly compared to 2016, may suggest a certain distancing, emotional and otherwise, adopted in pandemic reporting.

Border narratives on Europe

The second set of key narratives examined are those associated with the construction of Europe and perceptions of Europe.

Crisis in/of Europe: incapable EU

Central to this narrative is the portraying of the EU as an actor incapable of handling migration. The newspaper 'Dolomiten' mainly cites Austrian politicians who cast the EU as unable to secure its external borders ("the EU is failing miserably", Günther Platter, president of Tyrol, 08/02/2016, "the EU has certainly failed here", Helmuth Spöttl, mayor of Nauders, 11/03/2016a) and who position Austria as victim forced to introduce border controls. Despite asserting that Austria is reluctant to implement such measures, the narrative strategically emphasizes a lack of alternatives or choices due to the EU's failing ("*We are being forced to introduce border controls 'that nobody wants'*", Günther Platter, president of Tyrol, 22/02/2016b, "*We are not jeopardising the open borders within the EU now, but the wrong policy from last year*" Sebastian Kurz, Austrian foreign minister, 02/03/2016).

"Austria is not stabbing the heart of Europe or any other heart' said Austrian President Heinz Fischer, correcting a corresponding statement by Italian Prime Minister Matteo Renzi. It was regrettable that Austria had to resort to self-help, so to speak". (Heinz Fischer, Austrian Federal President, 25/02/2016b)

Crisis of Europe: Europe threatened by internal/Schengen re-bordering

The narrative of "crisis of Europe" emphasizes the closure of internal EU Schengen borders as a threat. The principal concern lies not with the influx of migrants, but rather with the unilateral state decisions to strengthen border controls, resulting in a destabilizing effect on both the EU and the broader European community ("*Unilateral decisions by individual EU countries would cause serious damage to Europe*", Paolo Gentiloni, Italian foreign minister, 16/02/2016, "*A step backwards for the European unification process*", Arno Kompatscher, president of South Tyrol, 04/04/2016). The victims portrayed in the narratives are the EU, on the one hand, and the minority community who benefits from open Schengen borders on the other. In fact, this narrative is mainly constructed by representatives of the German-speaking minority in South Tyrol who cast re-bordering as a negative act that is infringing upon shared EU fundamental principles. The narrative underscores the importance of the EU for the minority and the border region associated with de-bordering. It highlights the economic benefits of de-bordering, such as preservation of cross-border flows and free movement of EU citizens, as well as political benefits of de-bordering, such as peace, stability, and reconciliation. This hints towards a perception of the EU as promoter of minorities and as an arbitrator in conflicts.

"Europe is important for South Tyrol. For South Tyrol, Europe means that the once unjustly created border at the Brenner Pass is open, it means peace and the basis for our prosperity. Europe must not fall back into petty statehood, that would be bad for South Tyrol". (Arno Kompatscher, president of South Tyrol, 09/07/2016)

“Europe does not need new internal borders, but rather a strengthening of the European guiding principle, which has guaranteed peace and prosperity for the continent over the last 70 years”. (Philipp Moser, president of the economic association *Südtiroler Wirtschaftsring*, 14/04/2016)

“Europe must work together to find a solution that strengthens an open Europe without internal borders”. (Hannes Baumgartner, vice-president of FERCAM Logistics & Transport, 05/05/2016)

Gated Europe: protecting and reinforcing EU external borders

Various narrators criticize the EU’s lack of a common approach in handling migration and call for a common European solution, generally remaining at the abstract level rather than proposing a concrete suggestion. Both minority and kin state narrators present the reinforcement of external EU borders as possible solution (kin state actors are coded twice as often as minority representatives with the narrative “gated Europe”). This spatial narration on Europe emphasizes the EU’s external borders as the boundaries of Europe, with a particularly big emphasis on preserving and shielding European identity against “the outside”.

“We need a common European refugee policy with protection of the external borders and more money for the countries of origin so that people stay there.” (Dieter Steger, SVP, 03/03/2016)

“The basic prerequisite for the removal of internal border controls must actually be secure (EU) external border controls. We have to wait and see”. (Johanna Mikl-Leitner, ÖVP, 11/03/2016b)

Minority political representatives also called for a better handling of the pandemic at the European level to avoid unilateral decisions by states and the resulting border closures.

Invisible narratives

One narrative was almost invisible in the coding process: that of an (in)humanitarian Europe/fortress Europe and its effect on migrants. Indeed, only 18 articles presented borders as threats to the lives of migrants, quoting primarily civil society organizations and church representatives. Coupled with the near absence of migrant or humanitarian narrators, and of narratives of “Fortress Europe”, this shows that in the case of South Tyrol, the public narratives constructed and presented by the minority daily newspaper ‘Dolomiten’ was first and foremost concerned with the (negative) impacts of bordering processes on “its own people”.

4.2 ‘Głos’ in the Polish-Czech Borderland

Authors: Elżbieta Opiłowska & Damian Bączkiewicz

4.2.1 Background Information

Our study concerned the Polish minority in the Czech Republic, primarily residing in the Zaolzie region (in Czech rather known as Těšínské Slezsko). The presence of Poles can be traced back to historical factors, particularly the geopolitical changes after World War I. Following the war, the boundaries of Central Europe were redrawn, leading to the creation of Czechoslovakia from the Austro-Hungarian Empire. The Zaolzie region, despite its predominantly Polish population, became part of Czechoslovakia due to political negotiations and territorial agreements based on a plebiscite won by the Czechs – the area of Cieszyn Silesia beyond the Olza River was granted to Czechoslovakia. Comprising approximately 10% of the population of the Zaolzie region, nestled in the northern part of the country, the Polish minority maintains its traditions, language, and customs, enriching the cultural tapestry of Czechia. Despite challenges in the past regarding cultural preservation and recognition, as well as the continuous decrease in the number of members of the minority, it continues to flourish, contributing to the diverse fabric of Czech society while cherishing its distinct heritage. While precise numerical estimations may vary, it is generally acknowledged that there exists a substantial population of ethnic Poles, numbering approx. 20,000–40,000 people.

According to the Czech Statistical Office and its Czech Republic's National Population and Housing Census, in 2021, 26 802 people declared their nationality as Polish (in the Moravian-Silesian Voivodeship, the figure reached 18 378). In addition, 9,814 people entered a dual nationality on the form - Polish and Czech and 1294 together with other nationalities (Moravian, Slovakian, Ukrainian, Vietnamese, Russian, European, Silesian, German and Roma).

Table 8: Polish minority in the Czech Republic

Nationality	2021	2011
Polish	26,802	39,269
Polish & Czech	9,814	2,809
Polish and other	1,294	568
Total	37,910	42,646

Source: Głos, 4, 14/01/2022, p. 1.

There are several official and non-governmental organizations representing the Polish minority in Czechia, such as the Polish Cultural and Educational Union (Polski Związek Kulturalno-Oświatowy w Republice Czeskiej, PZKO), Congress of Poles in the Czech Republic (Kongres Polaków) and Books Discussion Club (Dyskusyjny Klub Książki).

Established in 1945, 'Głos' stands as the preeminent Polish-language newspaper in Czechia, curated and published by the 'Congress of Poles,' the official organization representing the Polish minority. With a circulation of 5,000 copies per edition, it holds a vital position in preserving and disseminating Polish culture and news in the Czech Republic. Transitioning to a modern era, 'Głos' adapted by going digital, offering full online access while also embracing a robust social media presence under 'Głos.live.' Its active engagement on platforms like Facebook (approx. 7,000 followers), Instagram (1,000 followers), YouTube (550 subscribers), and Twitter (350 followers) allows for broader outreach, transcending traditional print boundaries. With its twice a week publication, 'Głos' remains a pivotal source, fostering the cohesion and visibility of the Polish minority in Czechia through its comprehensive coverage and digital accessibility.

In total, 124 editions¹ of the newspaper published in 2015 and 2020 were analysed, of which 79 editions were published in 2015 (July – December) and 45 editions in 2020 (March – August). These two periods cover key moments for the region and correspond to both the so-called 'migration crisis' as well as the parliamentary elections in Poland of 2015 that had some significant impact on Czech politics and the 2020 lockdown period resulting from the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic and the related restrictions on border crossing, which particularly affected cross-border workers in this area.

It is difficult to consider all articles of equal length and validity. However, in total, the analysis covered 165 articles referencing 'border' (with the keyword 'granic[a]' in Polish) or 'Europe' and the 'European Union'. Within this set, 89 references were found during the refugee crisis of 2015 and 76 articles from the onset of the pandemic in 2020.

4.2.2. Narratives on Borders and Europe

Articles devoted to border issues were very rarely the centre of attention for the newspaper's editors. Out of 165 analyzed articles, only 17 of them included the word 'border' in the headline or title. Slightly less, 16 articles, concerning borders were placed on the first page, especially those that concerned the issue of border crossing during the pandemic of 2020.

The analysis of the frequency of codes regarding borders in the newspaper showcases varying emphases:

- 'Border as fence' emerged prominently with 96 references, indicating a focus on physical barriers and security measures related to the migration crisis and the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic.
- 'Border as bridge' was referenced 55 times, highlighting the symbolic role of borders as connectors and the cross-border integrated area.
- 'Border as bridge – cultural cross-border cooperation' was applied 44 times, indicating various transborder initiatives and projects.
- 'Identity shaper' appeared 10 times, signalling the border's influence on cultural and national identities.
- 'Othering' was referenced 26 times, suggesting narratives that create divisions or distinctions between social groups.

- 'Site of transgression' and 'De-/Re-bordering' were mentioned 9 and 11 times respectively.
- As for the level of the border, the national level with 36 references dominated the results, followed by local references (between twin city at the state border) (23) and Schengen (23).
- Border as 'immunological barrier' was referred to 15 times and as a 'site of transgression' – 9 times.
- Regarding 'Europe', one code has been added during the analysis, namely 'EU as instrumental actor' presented mostly as a fund provider. It was applied 18 times.
- References to 'Crisis in Europe' totalled 13, indicating discussions surrounding crises impacting the continent in relation to migration and 'Gated Europe/Fortress Europe' was mentioned 7 times.
- 'Open/Humanitarian Europe' was noted 8 times, potentially representing narratives emphasizing Europe's humanitarian efforts or values in relation to providing support to migrants.
- Moreover, the code "Minority as bridge" was added and applied 13 times which emphasizes the role of minority in bilateral relations between Czechs and Poles.

Figure 4: Types of borders mentioned in 'Głos' and its narrators

Figure 5: Main narrations about Europe and minorities identified in 'Głos' and their users

Figure 6: Main narrations about border identified in 'Głós' and their users

Types of narrators and narratives

The authors of the narrative about border and Europe were dominated by representatives of the political class, mainly, in 40 cases, national / state politicians (32 male, 8 female) such as prime ministers and ministers of Poland and the Czech Republic. Less frequently (out of 35 cases, 25 male and 10 female) the voice was given to local politicians representing the national majority, 12 times to cross-border institutional actors and 3 times to the politicians of foreign origin. In turn, voices of representatives of the minority were included (28) representing predominately civil society and non-governmental organizations. Economic actors were asked the least frequently (6 times in total) and two voices of EU actors were also rarely presented (2 times). In all cases the male producers of narratives on borders and Europe dominated discussions. Of all the 162 references to narrators found, a staggering 72% belonged to men, while a female narrative featured in only 28%, almost three times less frequent. This ratio

disadvantaging women's voices is also evident if we look at statistics taking into account only male and female politicians at local, regional and national levels. Of the 80 references to this political discourse, 74% (59 times) were made by men and 21 times by women - 26% of the references to politicians' opinions.

We could see that there was a strong correlation between the narratives and their authors. National and local politicians of both Polish and Czech origin remained the main producers of published narratives about the need to rethink the border crossing (bordering and immunological borders codes). At the same time, Polish and Czech politicians from both sides of the border quoted by the newspaper expressed similar views. This can be explained by their likewise approach to European issues such as border protection or migration issues, which was a natural field for mutual understanding. It should also be noted that every quote about the crisis in Europe was expressed either by Prime ministers or ministers of, for example, foreign affairs who warned about Europe's future. Moreover, the idea of fencing Europe remained not a personal opinion nor a "commonly" shared idea, but something expressed only by quotes of the politicians from the national level. Whereas the inhabitants expressed in the analysed articles the need to re-open the borders as they remained a fence for free travel to visit family members and go to work. Furthermore, in three cases, inhabitants were quoted to show the local fear of creating a center for housing refugees. It's worth mentioning that we could find the idea of rebordering in only one article. Nevertheless, the author referred to this question in a historical context of post WWI changes of borders in Central Europe and the Polish-Czechoslovakian conflict. The code 'border as bridge' could be assigned mostly to voices of local actor as well as institutional cross-border actors. In many cases it is difficult to identify 'producers' of the narratives as the articles very often describe the situation while reporting on some events and not clearly indicate the agents of them.

It should be noted that a pair of codes often appeared: border national - border as a fence and Schengen border. Moreover, the ambivalent character of the border during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic could be extracted from codes pair border as bridge and border as fence. The code 'Schengen zone' was combined with statements of national politicians and "a border as a fence". 'Crisis in Europe' was accompanied by the code 'Schengen border'.

The surprising discovery was that 'Głos' in 2020 referred primarily to the borders in its local context —as a current fence and as a past bridge for local initiatives and the area of economic cooperation. The editors quoted local artists and wrote about their ideas of the local community linked by (not divided by) the border and emphasized the negative consequences of border closure for cross-border commuters. Furthermore, the predominant presence of local contexts and actors in 'Głos' was accompanied by lack of European issues and voices. Even if the codes 'Crisis in Europe', 'Gated/Fortress Europe' and 'Open/Humanitarian' Europe could be applied, the perspective of seeing these problems was rather local⁶.

⁶ One commonly cited example was the issue of the refugee camp in Ligota Górna.

The qualitative analysis of narratives derived from 'Głos' newspaper allows us to state that they represent primarily local topics and problems that concern the Polish minority and the local relationship between Poles and Czechs. It could even be claimed that the newspaper is very provincial and serves as a venue for publishing information on the activities of Polish minority organizations in Zaolzie region as well as on local events in the borderland. Both, the border, and Europe are not in focus of narratives. Whereas the former seems to be present only because of the geographical location of the minority close to the border, the latter is related either to EU funds or to the crisis caused by migration policy.

Moreover, it is necessary to note certain differences that occurred in both analyzed periods. In 2015, the focus was on borders as part of national affairs and competencies, where the border as a fence also became a means of differentiation. The border as a bridge was treated mainly in the context of the local community, and agreements between non-governmental organizations and local authorities; there was no strictly local context, i.e. crossing the physical border by residents. In individual cases, references to borders as a place where a crime was committed could be seen. Crucially, all narratives about Europe's crisis come from this period. It was then that concerns about the future of Europe were expressed through the statements of national politicians in the Czech Republic, Poland and, for example, Hungary. Thus, the migration crisis was seen as a problem of national or European actors and not as a local concern. The theme of migration appeared mostly because of refugee camp in Ligota Górna that aroused fears in the local community. At the time, 7 out of 8 examples of uses of the code 'open Europe' also come from this period (2015), but this narrative was an editorial comment, not a quotation from other sources. It is worth noting that even against this backdrop the need to remodel borders was not mentioned – such an idea was present once, but in the context of historic border changes in 1989.

In turn, 'Głos' issued in 2020 focused on closing the Schengen area, reopening closed border crossings and tearing apart local communities. The narrative on closed borders, borders as a fence concerned the local aspect, not the whole continent – Europe in crisis was never mentioned. More important in the narrative were the voices of cross-border workers who could not go to work or return home from work or local politicians and cross-border institutional actors who appealed to the Czech and Polish government to consider by decision making process the specific border context and cross-border practices of inhabitants. An interesting aspect here is the creation of a comparative pair of two opposing keywords – the border as a bridge and the border as a fence. The co-occurrence of these codes demonstrates the ambivalent character of the border, as presented in 'Głos' during the pandemic. It might be associated with a narrative about the previous invisibility of borders, which facilitated cultural and family exchange, and on the other hand, a gated border as a symbol of division and othering due to national status and a source of uncertainty. However, the uncertainty concerned local and family matters, and not the future of Europe or the European Union per se. Surprisingly, the issue of border, even if it was quite objectively important in the period of rebordering policies, was not particularly frequent for the analyzed newspaper. The newspaper's editors remained extremely supportive of the idea of keeping the borders open.

For example, there were two interesting articles about the crisis in Europe. The first one concerned the quoted statement of Hungarian Prime Minister Orbán, who criticized the attacks directed against his country in an attempt to stop the wave of migrants at the border:

“Hungarian Prime Minister Viktor Orbán emphasized in Brussels on Thursday that the only answer to the migration crisis is strengthened protection of European borders. According to the head of the Hungarian government, the proposed quotas for dividing refugees among the European Union member states allow immigrants to delude themselves that Europe will accept them all. He also appealed not to attack his country for trying to protect the EU’s borders. Hungary has previously been criticized for building a fence on the border with Serbia.” (Głos Ludu, 106, 05/09/2015, p. 1)

On the other hand, another edition of the newspaper published a report on the visit of Czech President Zeman, who, when asked about migration in Europe, said:

“I am in favor of remaining in the EU, provided that the EU does not engage in nonsense that should be the responsibility of nation states and their governments. Such nonsense includes quotas for the distribution of refugees in individual member states - said the president, lumping this problem into one bag with the European directive on water consumption in toilets (...) - If the EU stops dealing with such details and instead focuses on strategic issues, such as common foreign policy, common defence policy, including the protection of internal borders, which has not been successful so far, then I think that we should remain in the European Union”. (Głos Ludu, 115, 26/09/2015, p. 4).

In turn, an example of an article that showed the previous invisibility of borders, which allowed for free exchange, and compared it with the Covid restrictions in force at that time, was a text published in August 2020. It quoted a local Polish employee who compared the closing of the borders to Armageddon and was happy that the opening of the borders would make it possible for Poles to look for work in the Czech Republic. It is worth noting that chief editors of the newspapers took the perspective of cross-border workers what the following quote demonstrates:

“That’s right, countries... Because I am a cross-border worker, I felt in an instant how much they have grown in power. For example, they have closed their borders and worship. Fear of a pandemic also justifies the growing surveillance, as it is not only China that chooses to monitor its citizens. The mobile phones of infected citizens are tracked by Israel, for example. But Poland also has such capabilities. On top of this, in a matter of days, governments have launched anti-crisis solutions that would normally take many months to develop. We do not yet know whether the pandemic will devastate our economic and financial system. What we do know is that, as with terrorism, the European Union and the entire western world should fight the threat together.” (Głos, 29, 14/04/2020, p. 2).

The article titled "Fear of Refugees" published on the front page of the newspaper presented a surprising narrative. It discussed the proposal by the Czech local administration to alter the intended purpose of constructing a detention center in the area. Rather than a prison, they suggested building a specialized

facility for "illegal migrants". This proposal caused frustration among the local residents who preferred a prison over a refugee center. The article included strong statements from local residents who believed that it would be safer to build a prison there. They argued to have bad experiences with a camp which used to operate there by othering the refugees: *"The refugees wandered around the village, made a mess, went door-to-door and begged"*, *"Who knows what diseases the newcomers will bring here"*. (Głos Ludu 85, 15/07/2015, p. 1, 5)

As mentioned above, voices of female and European actors are poorly present. It does not mean that they are absent, but not very visible in narratives on border and Europe. Furthermore, based on the analyzed sources it can be argued that economic actors are not producers of border and European narratives in 'Głos'. With the 'migration crisis' in 2015, narratives were shaped by national actors, both Polish and Czech. It might be explained by the fact that this region did not experience directly the impact of migration on everyday life. The absence of the EU as well as the economic actors in 2020 is also interesting taking into account that many companies went bankrupt, and entrepreneurs complained about the decreasing income. However, their opinions were not quoted in contrast to inhabitants and cross-border commuters. Regarding narratives on Europe, even though "covid-fencing" impacted almost all border regions in the Schengen area, the problem was seen from the very local perspective. Whereas in 2015 'Głos' recognized the migration problem as 'Europe in crisis', in 2020 the European context in terms of joint achievements as free movement of people has been ignored and only the local dimension of the border closure was highlighted.

4.3 'Nordschleswiger' and 'Flensburg Avis' in the Danish-German Borderland

Author: Martin Klatt

4.3.1 Background Information

The Danish-German border region is defined as the former duchy of Schleswig, precisely as the Danish municipalities of Tønder, Haderslev, Aabenraa and Sønderborg and the German counties of Nordfriesland, Schleswig-Flensburg, the part of the county of Rendsburg-Eckernförde north of the Kiel Canal, the city of Flensburg and the part of the city of Kiel north of the Kiel Canal. The part of the region belonging to Denmark (North Schleswig) has a population of approximately 225,000 (March 2024), out of which an estimated 12,000-15,000 identify with the German minority. The part of the region belonging to Germany (South Schleswig) has a population of approximately 688,000 (Dec. 2022), of which an estimated 50,000 identify with the Danish minority. Minority affiliation is not recorded in any official data. The estimate is based on the rate of attendance of minority schools and has been stable over the last 30-40 years, except for a 10-20% increase of German minority school (in Denmark) attendance since 2020.

The Danish-German border region is characterized by its post WW I border settlement, where the geopolitical (border between the declining Danish and the rising German empire) as well as the linguistic-cultural-national conflict of the 19th century (the residents' individual affiliation with the dominant German cultural sphere or with the Danish national awakening) of the duchy of Schleswig was solved by dividing it between Denmark and Germany, in a division designed by Danish politicians and confirmed in a plebiscite. The dissenters of the plebiscite (about 25% in the part given to or reunited with Denmark, North Schleswig, had voted for Germany and 20% in the part remaining with Germany, South Schleswig, had voted for Denmark) were offered the opportunity to organize as recognized national minorities with a system of parallel institutions, primarily educational, but also other associations. While the settlement has remained controversial in the interwar period and immediately after WW II, Denmark and (West-)Germany agreed on a bilateral solution by unilateral declarations guaranteeing minority rights, subjective self-identification, and generous kin state support to finance minority institutions in 1955. This agreement opened for West Germany's accession to NATO and confirmed a new geopolitical situation shaped by the Cold War, where the Danish-German border lost its geopolitical significance. Minority-majority relations have improved continuously since, with some setbacks based on conflicts of resources. Today, relations are considered best-practice.

Two newspapers were selected for analysis to reflect the reciprocal kin-state-kin-minority situation in the region: 'Der Nordschleswiger' as the German minority's daily newspaper for the period September 2015-February 2016 and March-June and August 2020, and 'Flensburg Avis', the Danish minority's daily newspaper for the period September, October, December 2015, February 2016, and March 2020.

'Der Nordschleswiger' is the successor of 'Nordschleswigsche Zeitung,' which merged the German language media in North Schleswig in 1929. Starting as a conservative, national paper, it uncritically supported the Nazi takeover in Germany in 1933, advocated a border revision and supported the Nazi-German cause in WW II. 'Der Nordschleswiger' restarted German language press in North Schleswig in 1946 as a weekly paper, from 1951 to 2021 it was a daily paper (6 days a week). From 2021, it has been an online medium with a bi-weekly printed edition. Before moving online, the newspaper had around 1,100 subscribers.

'Flensborg Avis' is the oldest Danish-language paper in the region, founded in 1869. Since 1920, it has been the newly established Danish minority's newspaper. It is still published 6 days a week with a circulation of around 5,800 copies. The Thursday issue has about 15,000 copies and is circulated to all members of the two important cultural associations of the Danish minority, Sydslesvigsk Forening and Sydslesvigs danske Ungdomsforeninger.

The Danish media database Infomedia was used as source with the key words "Grenze" and "grænse" and their composites as Grenzschißung/grænselukning (border closure), Grenzkontrolle/grænsekontrol (border control), Grenzpendler/grænsependler (cross-border commuter) etc. Letters to the editor were excluded, as were articles only reporting notices (for example: "border crossing point XXX will re-open on Sunday") or referring to other meanings of the word Grenze/grænse than border: in both Danish and German it also translates to the English "limit".

Articles from two time periods were selected for the analysis: September 2015-February 2016 for reporting on the humanitarian crisis, and March 2020 ('Flensborg Avis') / March-June and August 2020 (Nordschleswiger) for the Covid period. Coding was stopped after a review of approximately 1,000 coded articles, at the point of data saturation. This has resulted in a bias towards 'Der Nordschleswiger' with about twice as many articles coded (621 coded articles vs 312 in 'Flensborg Avis'). When looking at the months analyzed for both papers, it is apparent that while both papers' coverage of "border" during Covid was comparable, there was significant more coverage of border-related issues during the migration crisis in 'Flensborg Avis' (77.5 coded articles per month) than in 'Der Nordschleswiger' (41.3 articles per month). This difference is also reflected in the numbers of all articles collected (including the articles published in months not coded) and may be explained by the different governmental as well as civil society approaches to migration (welcome culture in Germany vs. restrictive approach in Denmark), which challenged the self-identification of many Danish minority members and thus resulted in more coverage reflecting this dilemma.

4.3.2 Narratives on Borders and Europe

In about a third of the coded articles in Flensborg Avis in 2015-16, the topic of the border featured in the headlines (78 out of 266 articles), including 19 references on title pages. For 'Der Nordschleswiger' the number of articles mentioning the border in headlines was similar, 85 of 248 articles (34%), hereof 22 on

title pages. During the Covid-19 crisis, the percentage of headlines mentioning borders was even higher: almost two thirds in the case of 'Flensburg Avis' (27 of 45 articles, and on 3 title pages), and about 40% (159 of 375 articles, 43 of which on title pages) in 'Der Nordschleswiger'.

The following table provides a quantitative overview of the main border narratives presented in the newspaper articles analysed, in descending frequency. The table is divided to show the differences during the two time periods examined. The main narratives presented are those related to borders (border as bridge/fence/identity shaper/othering/site of transgression/de-bordering) and to Europe (crisis Europe/fortress Europe/humanitarian Europe).

Table 9: Quantitative overview of the main border narratives presented in the newspaper articles of 'Flensburg Avis' and 'Der Nordschleswiger'

Migration (2015-2016)	Flensburg Avis (n=266 articles)	Der Nordschleswiger (n=248 articles)	Aggregated (n=514 articles)
Border as bridge	277	195	472
Border as fence	188	130	318
Border as othering	56	44	100
Border as site of transgression	42	56	98
Humanitarian Europe	61	29	90
Crisis Europe	45	40	85
Fortress Europe	36	6	42
De-bordering	19	6	25
Border as identity shaper	8	7	15
Covid (2020)	(n=45)	(n=375)	(n=420 articles)
Border as bridge	45	467	512
Border as fence	42	221	263
De-bordering	1	209	210
Border as site of transgression	5	59	64
Border as othering	12	43	55
Border as identity shaper	4	32	36
Crisis Europe	3	31	34
Fortress Europe	4	16	20
Humanitarian Europe	2	16	18

In terms of the dominant narrators (see table 10 below), we only see minor differences between the newspapers. Overall, politicians were the main category of narrators in both newspapers and for both timeframes, and importantly often featured the same (Danish) politicians (who in the case of ‘Flensburg Avis’ would be kin state politicians” and “home state politicians” in ‘Der Nordschleswiger’). In the case of ‘Flensburg Avis’, local and regional economic actors also featured heavily during the humanitarian crisis. In both newspapers, the voices of migrants are largely absent from reporting.

Table 10: Most and least dominant narrators in ‘Flensburg Avis’ and ‘Der Nordschleswiger’

Migration	Flensburg Avis (n=268 articles)	Der Nordschleswiger (n=248 articles)
most dominant narrator	Economic actor (regional and local majority, male): 64	Politician home state (male): 41
most dominant narrator category	Politician: 212 Of which minority politician: 63	Politician: 199 Of which minority politician: 42
least dominant narrator category	migrants/refugees: 2	Migrants/refugees: 0
Covid		
	(n=45)	(n=375)
most dominant narrator	Politician kin state (male): 13	Politician home state (male): 62
most dominant narrator category	Politician: 33 Of which minority politician: 6	Politician: 363 Of which minority politician: 82
Least dominant narrator category	migrants/refugees (f+m): 0	migrants/refugees (f+m):0

For both periods, **the most common narrative is that of “border as a bridge”** (984 codes), while that of “border as a fence” comes to 581 codes. While the difference in the number of these two narratives is smaller during the humanitarian crisis (472 vs. 318 codes), it is very significant during the Covid crisis (512 vs. 263 codes). This may be explained by the fact that during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic the “border as a bridge” narrative was stressed as the strict border closures deeply affected the two minorities. This was not the case during the migration crisis, where re-bordering due to increased border controls had a psychological impact but did not hinder residents from crossing the border at any time they liked. The high number of articles referring to the border during the pandemic (about one code per newspaper issue) demonstrates the importance of the issue of re-bordering for the two minority newspapers.

Narratives on borders as a “threat” and “debordering” are mainly presented by economic actors as well as minority politicians. For other politicians, there is no clear correlation to either the narratives relating to open borders or to closed borders codes. In the migration crisis, male majority politicians in Denmark talked about the border as security device” in about a third of their statements (9 out of 26 references), while 3 out of 7 quotes of German majority politicians in ‘Flensburg Avis’ referred to “fence as a security

device". The narrative of the border as security device is also present during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic with Danish politicians adopting this narrative more so than German politicians.

Minority narrators frequently present "open border" narratives, portraying borders particularly as "threat" (306 references in minority narrations consider it as "threat", while the remaining 201 were associated to the following codes: "border as a bridge", "border as a fence", "border as identity shaper", "border as othering", "border as a site of transgression" and "border opening-debordering"). This applies to both newspapers and both minorities. Minority politicians mostly presented narratives of the "border as a bridge", whereas regional and local majority politicians did not present this narrative.

Finally, in terms of gender, there is a strong dominance of male narrators in both newspapers, particularly of politicians, as demonstrated in the graph below.

Figure 7: Gender distribution of coded narrators in the 'Flensburg Avis' and 'Der Nordschleswiger'

Many articles presented both "fence" and "bridge" narratives of borders. This indicates a sense of responsible journalism, as they quote and include informants with diverse opinions, giving a more balanced view on borders. In about half of the narratives of the border as bridge, either the economic or the cultural aspects of this bridging function were discussed. This applies for both periods. The location of the border also matters: The narratives related to opening and de-bordering tend to occur in relation to the local border or the national border. This reflects the minority language media's regional focus and their coverage of the immediate border situation and its impact on the minorities as well as the borderland population.

The narrative of "border as site of transgression" also figures rather prominently (64 references during the Covid-period) and appeared more frequently than, for instance, narratives of borders as identity shaper,

as othering as well as all codes related to the EU. For the migration crisis period, it was the second-most frequent code (98 references), with the most common being “othering” (100), and “open/humanitarian EU” with 90 references.

Narrators from local residents, civil society and local politicians, but also chief editors, mainly talked about the border as either a bridge or as a threat. While this attitude dominates for all border regional speaker categories, it is exclusive for minority speakers. There is a slight variation for the Covid-period, when the necessity to regulate and limit travel through border closures were accepted by the chief editors and prominent minority members and minority politicians as a temporary immunitary measure. However, this narrative was replaced by the “de-bordering” narrative about a month into the border closure, in mid-April 2020.

These “de-bordering” narratives focused strongly on the personal cross-border connections of borderlanders with family and friends on the other side, on border crossings as a part of daily life, and a perception of living in a cross-border region, which were challenged by the strict rules for border crossings during the pandemic:

“That's why I haven't crossed the border yet, even though I could have done so as a German living in DK. I could not get myself having to go through a border right through my homeland - and that includes northern and southern Schleswig - with questions about my reasons for crossing it.”
(inhabitant, f, ‘Der Nordschleswiger’, 13/06/2020)

The importance of an open border for the economy was another central narrative, with narrators criticizing politicians’ neglect of local economic interests and the exaggerated controls which were perceived as symbolic policies that did not reflect actual challenges:

“Last year, when a lot of people were pouring into our country, there was a reason to control things, and now that the influx has almost completely decreased, they're starting to do that - in my opinion, that's not really well thought out” (economic actor regional & local majority m, ‘Der Nordschleswiger’, 06/01/2016)

A centre-periphery cleavage was very present in Denmark during the Covid period, with a sentiment that “the politicians in Copenhagen” have forgotten or do not understand the border region and its special needs. This was voiced by minority members and minority politicians, but increasingly also by locally elected opposition majority politicians (at local, regional and state level). With Germany’s greater readiness to reopen the border, this was not the case on the German side of the border.

It is evident that the newspapers report border narratives in a primarily local or bilateral context which is part of their agenda as regional newspapers. This might explain why narratives of Europe are not very prominent even though both the humanitarian crisis and the pandemic, and the resulting re-bordering policies, affected the whole of Europe. Narratives of Europe were more present during the migration crisis than during the pandemic, a reason being that the re-bordering during the migration crisis did not affect

borderland residents as they were not hindered in crossing the border. This was the case, however, during the pandemic, with Covid-induced re-bordering having a much higher impact on borderland living than the border controls introduced in January 2016.

Rebordering as a result of the humanitarian crisis thus appeared have a stronger impact on perceptions of Europe than did the effective border closures during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. The dilemma emerged of Europe as an open vs. as a closed society, and between the concept of open borders (Schengen), on the one hand, and migration control or a joint European migration policy, on the other. Covid-fencing, instead, highlighted the local aspect and shaped local perceptions of cross-border regions or minority-kin state relations coming under threat:

“North Schleswigers and Schleswig-Holsteiners live their everyday lives on both sides of the border: family, work, shopping, culture - one here, the other there in a unique borderland patchwork that is not even present to most state politicians.” (chief editor, m, ‘Der Nordschleswiger’, 22/04/2020)

Migrants and refugees were one category of absent voices – they did not appear at all during the Covid period and were very marginal (two references) also during the humanitarian crisis. Children and youth voices were also clearly underrepresented. Completely absent were narrations from economic actors at EU level. This can be partially explained by the economic fabric in the region, where companies, while operating internationally, are family businesses or with a very strong family component in their shareholder community.

4.4 'Új Szó' and 'Felvidék.ma' in the Slovak-Hungarian Borderland

Author: Péter Balogh

4.4.1 Background Information

The ethnic Hungarian minority of Slovakia is largely concentrated along the country's borders to Hungary. While Hungarian communities can be found all along this 650km-long boundary, they tend to be most sizable in southwestern Slovakia (Balogh & Pete 2018). In Slovakia's latest census (2021), 422,065 individuals declared Hungarian ethnicity and 462,165 Hungarian as their mother tongue. These figures equal to the respective shares of 7.75% and 8.48% among Slovakia's population (5.45m). While both the absolute number and share of this community have slowly but gradually decreased compared to previous censuses, the recent figures still imply that Hungarians constitute the country's largest ethnic minority. The latter statement can only be nuanced by noting the phenomenon that due to their stigmatisation, many Roma in Slovakia (whose official share is just 1.23%) indicate either Slovak or Hungarian ethnicity in censuses which leads to their numerical underestimation (Lášticová & Findor, 2016, p. 235).

Since Slovakia's independence in 1993, issues related to the Hungarian minority have been the key – though obviously not the only – element of Slovak-Hungarian ties. These relations have seen their ups and downs, experiencing low points around 1993–98 and 2008–11, but have overall improved in recent years. This is largely thanks to the general post-98 democratisation of Slovakia and the cautious but ongoing official bilingualisation process at least on the level of municipalities. In 2010, when Hungary altered its dual citizenship law to allow a simplified naturalisation process largely for ethnic Hungarians in its neighbouring countries, Slovakia immediately banned dual citizenship for its citizens. A few Slovakian Hungarians have reportedly still obtained Hungarian passport, which first led to considerable tensions between the two nations but was later downplayed by former Slovak President Čaputová (Fv 190717). Since both countries joined the EU (2004) and Schengen (2007), cross-border mobility has intensified, with many bridges having been (re)built along the rivers Danube and Ipel which roughly constitute the western half of this long border.

Despite a potential readership of below half a million people, there is a plethora of Hungarian-language media in Slovakia. Ten different portals have been identified, the majority of which set up over the past decade. This growth is also related to the fact that several of the more recent portals are openly supported by the Hungarian government, which also constitutes the main fault line between these media. As only a minority of the portals publicise data on their traffic and readership, a more comparable indication of their outreach is their number of followers on Facebook (which remains the most popular social medium in the region). In early May 2024, the two portals with the most followers were 'Új Szó' (95,000 followers) and 'Felvidék.ma' (74,000). These two are also politically diverging and thus constitute a good selection for this report. In the citations of their articles, 'Új Szó' is abbreviated to ÚSz and 'Felvidék.ma' to Fv.

‘Új Szó’ is by far the oldest (established in 1948) and still operating Hungarian-language medium in Slovakia. It is a daily newspaper still issued in print (20,000 copies/day) in addition to having an online edition, ujszo.com (10 million page downloads/month). Accordingly, the outlet claims to be the most frequently visited Hungarian-language portal in Slovakia, as well as the second most read daily paper (of all) in two out of the country’s eight Regions, Trnava and Nitra, which largely make up southwestern Slovakia. The outlet does not explicitly side with any political party or ideology, but it tends to be critical of the incumbent governments of both Slovakia and Hungary. Overall, it gives the impression of a ‘mainstream’, centrist outlet. Among the Hungarian government-supported media in Slovakia, ‘Felvidék.ma’ by far appears to have the widest readership (see above). It has been online-based ever since it began operating in 2006, and its leaning is generally national-conservative.

The temporal delimitation of this analysis has been roughly pre-defined by the methodological framework outlined in section 3 – the refugee and Covid crises. Thus, for the first period I selected the months June–December 2015, which coincide with the so-called migration or humanitarian crisis. I delimited the second period to March–October 2020, as Hungary ended its temporarily reintroduced border controls on October 31 (Fv 01/10/2020). I used the archives of both news portals to access articles containing the Hungarian equivalent of the term ‘border’ (*határ*). It should be noted that no meaningful Hungarian equivalents of the terms ‘de- and re-bordering’ exist. Yet, I also searched for the terms ‘border barrier’, ‘refugee crisis’, ‘migrant/migration crisis’, and ‘Europe’. In these endeavours, two minor challenges were encountered: the first one relates to the search engine of one of the portals, and the second one concerns Tables 2 and 3, the rigid categories of which can – to varying degrees – always be questioned (see below).

Table 11 (below) indicates the temporal distribution and source of the 150 analysed articles, showing that these are evenly distributed between the two media and the two periods under investigation. At the same time, there is some imbalance within the two respective periods, as for the 2015 period more relevant articles were identified in ‘Felvidék.ma’ than in ‘Új Szó’ which might reflect the fact that national-conservative media tend to pay more attention to migration- and border-related issues. As a counterbalance, more articles in ‘Új Szó’ were taken into account for the 2020 period – which however appears less politically divisive – than in ‘Felvidék.ma’. Regarding the length of the articles, when printed most of them are in the range of 2–5 pages.

Table 11: The number of articles analysed in ‘Új Szó’ and ‘Felvidék.ma’

Article sources / periods of investigation	Új Szó (ujszo.com)	Felvidék.ma	Total
2015 period	30	45	75
2020 period	48	27	75
Total	78	72	150

4.4.2 Narratives on Borders and Europe

Border-related topics feature intensively in the analysed media, including the headlines. This is hardly surprising given that Slovakia’s ethnic Hungarian community is concentrated along the long border, with which its life is accordingly strongly intertwined. In ‘Új Szó’, the term ‘border’ appears in 494 articles published in the first period and in 177 articles in the second. The archive of ‘Felvidék.ma’ is less user-friendly as it does not allow period selection. Accordingly, just searching for the term ‘border’ shows 33,602 articles published between December 2007 and early March 2024. At least the articles are indicated in a chronological order, allowing the searcher to move to the two periods of interest here. As this still results in lots of articles listed, I narrowed the search to the terms indicated in the previous paragraph, which led to more manageable numbers of hits.

In both media, some articles are provided with author names, and some are not. Many of the articles analysed are regular news articles, but some are commentaries, a few are categorised (by the media themselves) as ‘party media’, and a very few represent readers’ opinions. The latter three groups of articles are always provided with names. Overall, a clear majority of the articles were written by men. Based on a number of different social categories, Table 12 below shows the results of my quantitative analysis of whose voices are represented in the 150 articles analysed. The overall picture emerging is quite clear: ethnic Hungarian men are by far overrepresented, as are elites in politics and public administration. It is noteworthy though that the two media differ in two aspects. One is that the gender balance is somewhat more even in ‘Új Szó’ than in ‘Felvidék.ma’. Secondly, ‘Új Szó’ tends to give voice to more ‘regular citizens’ or residents (categorised below as non-elites/everyday citizens) than ‘Felvidék.ma’. Other than that, there are no major differences between the two media in these regards.

Table 12: The numbers of different categories of actors quoted in the articles of ‘Új Szó’ and ‘Felvidék.ma’

<i>Number of given category quoted (right); period (below)</i>	"border" in headline	women	men	ethnic Slovaks	ethnic Hungarians	persons other than Slovak or Hungarian	elites in politics or public admin.	NGO representatives	academics or experts	socio-economic elites	non-elites (everyday citizens)
Új Szó 2015	8	19	23	7	31	4	20	1	1	1	17
Felvidék 2015	2	7	75	38	30	16	66	8	2	1	2
Új Szó 2020	17	29	72	21	75	4	57	4	11	5	21
Felvidék 2020	12	6	37	5	39	1	31	4	3	1	4
Total	39	61	207	71	175	25	174	17	17	8	44

As an effort to try to quantify the articles’ content, certain distinguishable narratives are ‘translated’ into mutually agreed, pre-defined codes. Accordingly, a survey was performed also for this case, the results of which are summarised in Table 13 below. Ten different codes were applied, but we here restrict ourselves to a brief analysis of the five most prevalent ones. The most frequent theme was ‘border opening/debordering’. This is on the one hand related to longer-term processes in the border area (due to Schengen etc.), and to the importance placed on the gradually reopening borders (especially during Covid) on the other. The different degree of emphasis on this between the two media is noteworthy. The

second most common theme was ‘border as fence’, which mirrors the choice of the two ‘crisis’ periods being investigated. The third most often appearing narrative was ‘border as bridge’, which also mirrors longer-term integration efforts. Here again, though, the difference between the two media cannot remain unnoticed. The latter observation is even more valid for the fourth most common trope, that of ‘crisis in Europe’ (which was carefully distinguished from ‘crisis of Europe’, a notion barely present in any of the two media). ‘Felvidék.ma’ articles clearly presented the state of Europe in more apocalyptic ways than did ‘Új Szó’ ones. Finally, the fifth most often appearing theme was ‘border as othering’, with the two news portals here diverging during the 2015 period only.

Table 13: The presence of certain (predefined) narratives - translated as codes - in the articles of ‘Új Szó’ and ‘Felvidék.ma’

<i>Codes potentially present in the articles (right); periods (below)</i>	border as bridge	border as fence (barrier)	border as identity shaper	border as othering	border as site of transgression	border opening-debordering	crisis in Europe	crisis of Europe	gated/ Fortress Europe	open/ humanitarian Europe
Új Szó 2015	11	2	1	3	4	18	2	1	0	7
Felvidék 2015	2	8	3	14	14	1	24	5	13	11
Új Szó 2020	10	16	8	3	1	23	0	1	1	0
Felvidék 2020	4	14	5	3	1	11	0	0	2	1
<i>Total</i>	27	40	17	23	20	53	26	7	16	19

All methods have their shortcomings, including this one. The above-mentioned fifth most common theme is illustrative: while narratives of othering are very important in general, elaborating on who exactly is othered would have required a more nuanced approach. In fact, the target of othering did not only differ between the two periods (with 2015 seeing a focus on non-Europeans), but also the given context. Accordingly, othering could have many targets: the majority population, supranational bodies (such as the EU), the kin state, as well as political opponents within the minority community. Another issue encountered with this simple quantification was that acts of othering, border fencing etc. by different actors were indeed accounted for in the articles, but not always necessarily with a positive framing. To counterbalance some of these shortcomings, we now turn to the qualitative part of our media analysis.

The 2015 period as portrayed in ‘Új Szó’

In early June, ‘Új Szó’ published the opinions of three readers (two female and one male) in an article titled ‘How many refugees should Slovakia accept?’ (ÚSz 01/06/2015). The first one stressed that most refugees do not want to stay in Slovakia anyway, and that other countries’ experiences with migration should be taken into account. The second reader was *“not against accepting refugees but did not want the situation to get out of control”*. She also referred to some borderlanders’ worries that *“the refugees would not be placed in the more developed parts of the country but in the poorer districts”*. The third one found it difficult to say but stressed that the management of this complex issue should remain in the hands of each EU member state.

Also in June, an article spread Pope Francis's universal call against shutting out refugees (ÚSz 150617). Another article reported how *'the Council of Europe found Hungary's plan to build a border fence ill-advised'* (ÚSz 18/06/2015). In an opinion piece (ÚSz 26/06/2015), the female author reacted to a recent and reportedly very hateful anti-refugee march in Bratislava, in which neo-Nazis had partaken. She called on the government to support marginalised groups instead of exploiting their frustrations. In another opinion piece (ÚSz 27/06/2015), the male guest author from Hungary argued that the soon-to-be re-bordered Serbian-Hungarian borderland constitutes 'our Lampedusa', and that the politicisation of the refugee issue was the latest card in the hands of Hungary's government to halt its declining popularity, which results from the general sense of corruption and nepotism.

In July, a long article (ÚSz 20/07/2015) analysed local reactions to the refugee question and what they could say about and imply for minority-majority relations more broadly. According to the author:

*"The migrant issue and East Central Europeans' vehement reactions to it is decreasing the already limited capability to imagine a receptive and open Europe by the residents of our region... Few things irritate public opinion as much as minorities getting any form of real or imagined extra support from the state (as the Roma could tell) ... To many people, the migrant is 'the n[***]' – i.e., somebody I've never had a beer with but who I'm sure is primitive and violent. Again, our Roma friends could tell a lot about this... By politically approving an anti-migrant public atmosphere, we're creating a country in which the majority senses an opportunity to turn against minorities. As a member of a minority, I don't need to explain what sort of dangers this carries with itself... Moreover, the issue is dividing Europe, yet if Europe loses its receptiveness and empathy... we may once again be wondering who we are."* (ÚSz 20/07/2015)

August saw a report (ÚSz 14/08/2015) on a rather unconventional form of cross-border solidarity. The months before had seen the tripling of the number of refugees in a camp in Vámoszabadi on the Hungarian side, with locals heavily protesting. According to the mayor (female), this was because *"the migrants were loud, stealing fruits"* (ibid.) and committing atrocities on local buses to Győr (a larger city nearby). Yet, the county police did not sense a rise in the number of notifications received. According to the mayor, local tensions were also due to a lack of information from higher levels, which tended to neglect local concerns and proposals such as having more buses running. She also thought that a *"pan-European solution would need to be looked for"*. In the meantime, she and locals were empathetic with the likewise protesting residents of Gabčíkovo on the other side of the border, who were experiencing very similar challenges (see details in the next section).

Finally, although the coverage of the refugee issue is mixed in 'Új Szó', the reports on re-bordering trends contrast to many other border-related articles which depict a region which is ever more de-bordered: thousands were commuting across the border (ÚSz 150610); shopping tourism was flourishing (ÚSz 11/06/2015); up to 150 Hungarian scouts from Slovakia were camping in Hungary (ÚSz 16/08/2015); more buses will traffic the Bratislava–Rajka (NW Hungary) route to accommodate cross-border commuters (ÚSz 30/09/2015); the number of Slovak citizens had doubled in 15 years in Rajka, where people cohabit

peacefully (ÚSz 01/12/2015); and the town of Veľké Kapušany had gained a new sibling town in Hungary (ÚSz 27/12/2015).

The 2015 period as portrayed in ‘Felvidék.ma’

As a sort of prequel, it can be mentioned that ‘Felvidék.ma’ already reported in February that ‘*controls have been tightened along the Slovak-Hungarian border due to the refugees*’ (Fv 19/02/2015). Citing Slovakia’s Minister of Interior, a May headline was that ‘*Bratislava does not want African refugees*’ (Fv 19/05/2015). In June, Slovak PM Fico claimed that ‘*Hungary deserves respect for managing the refugee issue*’ (Fv 20/06/2015).

A key event that triggered a chain of more specifically borderland-focused attitudes and processes was the announcement of a Slovak-Austrian agreement in July to relocate 500 ‘migrants’ from Austria to Gabčíkovo, a town in southwest Slovakia whose residents are about 80% ethnic Hungarians. It is noteworthy how several articles (Fv 13/07/2015, Fv 11/08/2015) stress that Gabčíkovo is located on the ‘Hungarian-Slovak border’ (note the order). Crucially, fearing a spread of diseases as well as risk of terrorism, locals began protesting against the relocation, with an entrepreneur initiating a petition (Fv 13/07/2015). Rather unexpectedly in a Hungarian-government-supported medium, one of its articles (ibid.) also reported the following:

“The APA [Austrian Press Agency] had asked the project leader about his personal opinion on locals objecting to migrants being placed in Gabčíkovo. Mr Jaroš [a Slovak surname] explained that locals are informed by ‘fake news’, with many Hungarian-speaking residents of Gabčíkovo developing their image of the refugee situation based on news of Hungary-based TV channels.” (Fv 13/07/2015)

Here again, poor communication between different territorial-administrative levels appears to have made things worse. The mayor of Gabčíkovo claimed local concerns were legitimate given that not even he himself had been informed on the planned procedure through official channels (Fv 13/07/2015). This was also lamented by the deputy head of Most–Híd, a centrist Slovak-Hungarian party, who said the Slovak PM should avoid using discriminatory language against refugees and instead communicate with citizens in Gabčíkovo and elsewhere to dissolve their fears (Fv 24/07/2015). By late July, enough locals had signed the above-mentioned petition for a local referendum to be held on the issue, which was supported by the Party of the Hungarian Community (MKP) (Fv 31/07/2015), then the main (and conservative) ethnic Hungarian party in Slovakia. The referendum was held in early August and 58.5% of those eligible participated, 96.7% of whom rejected the reopening of the refugee camp (Fv 02/08/2015). However, Slovakia’s government declared the referendum results as non-binding (ibid).

Accordingly, in September the first two dozen refugees were transported from Austria to Gabčíkovo – reportedly against their will, as in Austria they had started taking German-language courses etc. (Fv 17/09/2015). The relocation was also lamented by MKP, stressing that ‘Hungarian-inhabited southern

Slovakia has got disproportionately many immigration institutions', thus urging a balanced domestic distribution (ibid).

In late August, fears were again mounting in Gabčíkovo. The far-right People's Party Our Slovakia was reported to be organising a protest march 'against the Islamisation of Europe', with cars and bikes rallying from Trnava to Gabčíkovo (Fv 29/08/2015). On the same day, the Hungary-based irredentist Sixty-Four Counties Movement planned a counterdemonstration in Gabčíkovo, whose mayor regretted both events and desperately called on locals to avoid them (ibid). Despite these understandable initial worries, nothing was later reported on these events.

More broadly, the refugee crisis also triggered some inter-minority tensions as well as majority-minority debates. PM Fico had declared that '*Slovakia could not even fully integrate its Roma yet, so it would be difficult to try the same with North Africans*' (Fv 11/08/2015). This opinion was reiterated by an ethnic Hungarian journalist (Fv 16/09/2015a), who went on to reflect about the (alleged) position of his own community in Slovakia:

"Why do these great sympathisers [with migrants] think they would integrate? Meanwhile, us minority Hungarians are here: why don't they show solidarity with us? Has anyone seen a demonstration at which the country's majority has stood with us? For instance, against the closure of Hungarian[-language] schools... Or, has anyone seen a demonstration for allowing Hungarian [place] names at railway stations? ... I don't think we'll see any such in the near future, but we would already be satisfied if our rights and expectations were respected. We've been here for a long time, and we are also working here and paying taxes." (Fv 16/09/2015a)

In a similar vein, an ethnic Hungarian politician pointed out what he sees as an important distinction between autochthonous minorities and more recent arrivals (16/09/2015b), strongly criticising the EU for not wanting to care about the former: *"How will we, or the Hungarians of Transylvania or Transcarpathia have autonomy? How and when does Brussels want to deal with this when all its strength is devoted to the wave of migrants?"*

Finally, despite the overwhelmingly negative coverage in 'Felvidék.ma', a few positive aspects appeared as well. It was reported that the Pope (Fv 09/09/2015), the Slovak Catholic Caritas and Slovakia's Episcopacy (Fv 10/08/2015) had called on parishes and citizens to accept refugees, to which the priest of Gabčíkovo at least reacted positively (Fv 09/09/2015). But in another piece (Fv 15/09/2015), a journalist was less fond of these ideas, claiming that *"Europe is progressing toward suicide' and that 'the culture, spirituality and customs of Europe will vanish"*. Arguing similarly, the MEP of MKP said it was *"a sin that the top European leaders do not sufficiently deal with the refugee issue... which should be stopped"* (Fv 23/08/2015).

The 2020 period as portrayed in 'Új Szó'

At the beginning of the first Covid wave, an article (ÚSz 14/03/2020) reported that *“the minor border-crossing points had been closed while the major ones were under continuous monitoring”*. The male journalist claimed that *“the majority of people is happy with the measures”* but cited only the opinion of two persons (both men). One of them said he was not happy about the extra kilometres he had to drive, but *‘he has acquaintances in Italy and does not want to get into a similar situation as them’* (ibid). The other one said *‘nothing good can be expected for the economy, but the virus can only be tamed through drastic measures’*.

Toward the end of the first wave, an article (ÚSz 15/05/2020) reported that eleven mayors of southern Slovakian cities had sent a letter to the incumbent Slovak PM *‘asking the Slovak govt to reconsider the restrictions on crossing the border between Hungary and Slovakia as soon as possible’*. The signatories provided several reasons for doing so. One is that there used to be *‘a very lively and active traffic’* across this border. Relatedly, the closure is *“affecting economic life and also dividing families”* (ibid). They also did not understand why:

Hungary is left out when Slovakia is already preparing to open its borders toward Czechia and Austria, as the number of cases does not justify this... In case a mini-Schengen will be realised, we are decidedly asking to include Hungary in this process. Since relations between Slovakia and Hungary are ordered and good, we do not see any barrier to this. (ÚSz 15/05/2020)

This article is of interest from a gender perspective as well. Of the eleven signatories only two are women, indicating an overwhelming prevalence of male mayors in southern Slovakia.

The beginning of the second wave also saw joint efforts of borderland elites in combating border closures. An article (ÚSz 01/09/2020a) published a joint letter formulated by two ethnic Hungarian and one bi-ethnic parties, this time appealing not to Slovakia’s but to Hungary’s government, with the Foreign Minister being the addressee. The background was that Hungary was just about to reinforce its restrictions on border crossing. Long extracts from the letter follow:

Us Hungarians know that we can really only count on each other. The now enforced government decree on border closures is negatively impacting on Slovakian Hungarians from several angles. Slovakia has been performing well in taming the pandemic. In the Hungarian-inhabited regions the number of cases is well beyond the average. We therefore believe that alleviating the border closures would not considerably contribute to the spread of the virus... Although the current regulation provides some mobility, over the past days we have encountered dozens of cases hampering the everyday lives of cross-border workers and pupils to an extent that they require fast solutions... We are asking to consider the following proposals. The now five open border crossing points are too few, in some cases commuting workers need to travel 120km more... We suggest the widening of the 30km free-mobility zone... In the spring, people could cross for up to 24 hours without any distance-related restrictions – it would help a lot if this was reinstalled. Due to schools

starting it is worth considering the introduction of a special student status, given that thousands from Slovakia are attending university or upper-secondary school in Hungary. (ÚSz 01/09/2020a)

Relatedly, another article (ÚSz 01/09/2020b) reported that a state secretary in Slovakia's education ministry (a Hungarian named woman) had approached Hungarian authorities to inform them that cross-border pupils from Šahy now had to travel 70km extra to reach their schools. The challenges posed to pupils was particularly peculiar given that tourists from the Visegrád countries had received exemption from travel bans to Hungary. As also reported, pressure was mounting on the Hungarian govt to abandon its selective border closures not least by the European commissioners for internal affairs and justice, respectively.

The 2020 period as portrayed in 'Felvidék.ma'

At the beginning of the first lockdowns, a longer article (Fv 19/03/2020) reported about the situation in the divided border city Komárno/Komárom, diagnosing that 'the two Komárnos are one city' slogan was now an illusion as they were divided by a concrete fence. The local mayor (a Hungarian-named man) confirmed that it was '*Hungary that had fully closed the crossing point at Komárno*', which he hoped would be solved not least since Hungary's Foreign Minister originated from the city and thus fully understood its problems. He added that his counterpart in Komárom (male) was also working on this as "*now, Slovak citizens working on the other side had to travel over 100km extra*" (ibid). At the same time, according to Komárno's mayor "*the population had understood the need to follow the restrictions in order to protect their own health*". He also criticised Slovakia's Government Commissioner for Minorities (also a Hungarian-named man) for rebuking the population instead of making the necessary documents available in Hungarian as well as other minority languages. By contrast, the local police in his town "*had informed the population bilingually [through notice boards etc.] on all playgrounds and sportsgrounds*" (ibid).

About a month into the first lockdowns, a shorter analysis (Fv 16/04/2020) of a male MKP-board member claimed the pandemic could pose new opportunities for southern Slovakia. This began by lamenting the low share of the agricultural sector (2.5%) in the country's GDP, the increase of which would particularly benefit southern Slovakia. Hence, in order to protect domestic (often ethnic Hungarian) agricultural entrepreneurs, the politician advocated more strongly controlled intra-Schengen borders in the future.

Representing a contrary set of opinions, another article (Fv 04/05/2020) reported about the initiative 'Srdcom doma' (With our heart at home), which was strongly against the border closures. As the president of the initiative, a Slovak-named man, said: "*we see no reason for not lifting the border barriers... when cross-border workers in the immediate borderland can cross without any controls*". Moreover, "*with the border closures, many of us got isolated from our relatives, tearing apart entire families*" (ibid). They therefore called on Slovakia to allow EU citizens and their relatives to enter the country. Further, a legal expert of the initiative (a Slovak-named woman) raised doubts about the constitutionality of Slovakia's

measures – including banning foreign citizens to enter the country’s territory – which were harsher than those of the neighbouring states.

On September 1, when Hungary reintroduced border closures, several articles reported about the salient mess and frustration created in places like Šahy (Fv 01/09/2020a) and Komárno (Fv 01/09/2020b). In the latter, people had to wait two hours to cross the border as Hungarian police forces were initially strictly examining people’s documents, which they stopped doing later in the morning due to the chaos that had emerged (Fv 01/09/2020b). Like ‘Új Szó’, ‘Felvidék.ma’ also published the already-mentioned joint letter by the leaders of all Hungarian parties in Slovakia (Fv 01/09/2020c). Another article (Fv 01/09/2020d), titled “*Now we do not belong together*”, reported that the board of Ipoly Valley EGTC had urged “*the MPs of Nógrád County (in northern Hungary) to immediately remedy the situation*”. Like ‘Új Szó’, ‘Felvidék.ma’ (ibid.) also pointed out the paradox that while Czech tourists were allowed to enter Hungary, people from southern Slovakia were not. In the midst of all this, Hungary could not live up to some of its promised border re-openings, such as at Balassagyarmat (Fv 02/09/2020). Last but not least, an opinion piece (Fv 11/09/2020) elaborated in greater detail the paradox that even though Hungary had for a decade been ruled by a govt prioritising Hungarian-Hungarian cross-border ties, it is now protecting itself also against transborder Hungarians. Despite its ethno-nationalist tone, the opinion piece (ibid.) stressed that it was thanks to the Schengen Area that crossing borders had become part of many people’s everyday lives.

In lieu of conclusions

Although the content presented above may not be too surprising to people with at least some familiarity with the region, some components were indeed noteworthy or even surprising. One such element is that despite their different backgrounds, the two analysed media do not appear as divergent and polarising as those found in Hungary. There are clear differences between their contents, especially in the opinion pieces. They also give voice to slightly different groups of people, with ‘Új Szó’ for instance tending to cite more EU-level actors etc. The degree of difference may also be affected by the given issue covered, as the refugee crisis overall appears to have been more polarising than the Covid-induced border-related measures. Beyond the views represented, regarding the refugee crisis it is noteworthy that ‘Felvidék.ma’ initially (and despite the negative coverage from the outset) mostly used the term ‘refugees’ but later changed to ‘migrants’, which has been in line with govt-close media in Hungary. But even in the latter outlet criticism of the Hungarian government appears, which would very rarely – if ever – occur in government-close media in Hungary. So, overall, the content of the two analysed media differs, but not extremely.

Based on the articles, Slovakian Hungarians were generally unhappy with the border closures, which comes as little surprise considering the numerous (and likewise reported) cross-border ties that have emerged especially over the past two decades. As reported, various actors and organisations raised their voice against the 2020 border closures, including joint lobbying by and targeting various actors on different spatial levels. Still, people can relate to the border in paradoxical and multifaceted ways, based on their

(real or perceived) interests at any given moment. Accordingly, the overall picture that emerges is not black-and-white as the following two paragraphs illustrate.

Accordingly, it was somewhat surprising, and perhaps counterintuitive, that in 2020 Slovakian Hungarians reportedly supported the border closures. However, only one article explicitly claimed this (ÚSz 14/03/2020), and it represented the voice of only two citizens. Indeed, another article (Fv 19/03/2020) also mentioned that people had understood the need for the restrictions – but also here, this was the assessment of one mayor. Additionally, both articles appeared at the beginning of the Covid period in Europe and concomitant border closures. As seen above, people were later much more sceptical about the border barriers, which became contested by several different organisations.

It was also interesting, and again counterintuitive, that an influential Hungarian politician in Slovakia advocated more strongly controlled intra-Schengen borders (Fv 16/04/2020). This is clearly a protectionist effort aimed at lifting agro-enterprises which are often run by ethnic Hungarians, but the irony of an ethnic minority representative advocating for stronger internal borders (which would in this case divide his community from its kin state) cannot be lost on anybody.

Last and certainly not least, the perhaps most interesting elements were the minority-specific discourses during the analysed crises and border closures. In 2015, some right-leaning voices of the given minority lamented that while members of the ethnic majority showed solidarity with the refugees, many do not support strengthening the institutions of their autochthonous, minority fellow citizens. In 2020, frustration was rather targeted toward the kin state and its elite, which despite its long-time ethnonational commitment had let down its transborder ethnic kin by closing its borders also against them.

5. Discussion

Having presented the quantitative and qualitative results of the four case studies, we now proceed with a concise summary of the main results of the study and the comparisons that can be drawn between the case study regions, with a particular focus on the key narratives on borders and Europe and the narrators who present them, as well as on those who are absent.

5.1 Border Narratives Compared

The first aim of this comparative report was to investigate how borders are narrated in minority newspaper media in four European borderlands. We found, first, that in numerical terms narrations of borders and re-bordering issues were far more prominent during the periods of increased migration (2015-2016) than during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic: “migration-fencing” was thus debated more often than “covid-fencing” across most case study regions, with a greater variety of different narrators and perspectives. The high number of border(ing) narratives during the migration crisis and the relatively low presence of border narratives during the pandemic may suggest that the socio-economic impacts of border restrictions were perceived as more acceptable – or unavoidable - during the pandemic. It may also be the case that during the pandemic, other issues were deemed more important for reporting on than the physical border itself. For example, there were many newspaper articles which focused on infection rates, numbers of deaths, and restrictions of movement in the municipality.

An exception was the Danish-German case, where the re-bordering effects were perceived as more pronounced during the pandemic than during the migration crisis. The physical blockade of the border with the closure of about 75% of the crossing points led to people being cut off from the kin state (and thus from family and friends), and was a traumatic experience for many minority members, comparable, as some stated, to the erection of the Berlin Wall in 1961. For the first time since 1945, the border was closed to them, while the re-bordering actions of 2016 never affected legal residents of the border region (and, hence, minority members) and was thus more symbolic.

Secondly, we sought to identify which border narratives were used in the reporting on borders. The common coding scheme allowed for this comparative analysis. We note some differences between the content and substance of the narratives shared. The **border as a fence** was the most frequently reported narrative in both South Tyrol and the Polish-Czech borderland. In these cases, the “re-bordered” border was presented both as a necessary instrument to counter security concerns, but also as a possible threat to the socio-cultural and economic life of the population in the border area. Only in the Slovakian-Hungarian case study was debordering/open borders the most frequently recorded narrative. The narrative of the **border as a bridge** also featured prominently. In the Danish-German and Polish-Czech borderland, for example, newspapers often highlighted the transnational lifestyles of borderland citizens who made trips across the border during everyday life. Drawing upon narrations of feelings of connectedness, cross-border relations and initiatives, these articles, highlighted that the lives of everyday

citizens had been unfairly disrupted by the border closures, with particularly severe impacts for borderlanders compared to the rest of the population.

A further key border narrative was that related to the **economic threat** posed by closed borders. This was a particularly frequent narrative in the case of the proposed border fence at the Brenner border in 2016 in the 'Dolomiten' newspaper. The blame for the negative impact of rebordering on the local economy, particularly the tourism industry, was largely placed on the state level (at both the Austrian and Italian state), for a failure of dealing effectively with the increase in migration, leading to the need for border closures. Similarly, the wider European Union was also targeted as an institution falling short in its duties to protect state borders and national minorities from the unexpected threat of increased migration, thus provoking the re-emergence of state borders. In these cases, we saw particular attention paid to borderlanders' anxieties and worries (Roshier, 2022), including the proposed fence at the Brenner border between South Tyrol and Austria.

In each case study region, the specific location of the **border was described as a special place** with a unique identity. For example, the Brenner border was narrated as a distinctive place both for the local borderland minority but also for Europe more broadly: as a symbol of cross-border EU integration, it was framed in largely positive terms. The use of these narratives of borders as special places were used to justify why these borders, and their inhabitants, faced pressures and challenges that could not be understood by the states and national elites. For example, in the context of the German-Danish border region during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, it was claimed that elites in Copenhagen could not understand the pressures faced by the population living in the border area. In the case study regions of Poland and Slovakia, newspaper articles focused on the disruption caused by informal refugee settlements, and the plan to construct a refugee reception center in the area.

The Hungarian minority in Slovakia felt that their region had to contend with a disproportionately high number of facilities for immigration control because their region was perceived as a remote and "Hungarian" place in the eyes of Slovakian state elites. Thus, while **minorities** see the borderland region as a special place warranting protection, they **do not feel respected** or understood by state-level actors. This was illustrated in the breakdown of communication between state-level actors and local administrators in the Hungarian minority region in Slovakia with regards to the proposed refugee center, showing a disconnect between state actors and the national minority at the periphery.

5.2 Narratives on Europe Compared

This report also set out to study narratives of the EU within newspaper reporting on border and explored the role of key de- and re-bordering events in shaping perceptions of the European project in minority regions. Key results were the predominance of narratives on Europe in migration-related reporting over reporting during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, the disconnect between local concerns and European narratives related to rebordering processes, a perception of Europe primarily as an institution rather than

the context for common heritage, values and beliefs, and the attribution of responsibility for border policies as lying with the individual states rather than the European Union.

First, migration has emerged as a catalyst for heightened reporting and discussion about Europe across all the analyzed case studies, with narratives on Europe being far more numerous during the humanitarian crisis of 2015-2016 than during the pandemic. Several factors contribute to this. The temporal dimension plays a crucial role, as many states introduced border controls for the first time during the migration crisis, sparking debates about the future of a borderless Europe and the significance of borders. Moreover, the emotional dimension is significant, with fear of “the other” and security narratives permeating discussions surrounding migration. These emotional responses further amplify the visibility of migration-related topics in media coverage.

Secondly, the analysis of minority newspapers reveals a predominant focus on local or bilateral border narratives, which aligns with their agenda as regional newspapers. However, this local focus does not necessarily translate into a perspective of seeing Europe through a local lens. Instead, what emerges is a disconnect between the local and the European, with predominantly local reporting not engaging with narratives on Europe. Across newspapers such as ‘Der Nordschleswiger’, ‘Flensburg Avis’, and ‘Głos’, there is a notable absence of minority narrators addressing European concerns or the role of Europe in border policies and for minority populations.

Even when overarching themes such as the “Crisis in Europe”, “Gated/Fortress Europe”, and “Open/Humanitarian” Europe were applied, the perspective remains primarily local. The local and European dimensions are often portrayed separately, with little debate on how Europe influences border policies or minority experiences. Moreover, discussions about Europe’s role in managing migration, and the resulting rebordering processes, typically involve non-local narrators, particularly state-level politicians (eg. Czech Republic, Poland, Hungary), addressing non-local issues, further emphasizing the disconnection between the local and European spheres.

In contrast to this trend, the narratives presented in the ‘Dolomiten’ newspaper stand out as an exception. This could be due to South Tyrol’s strong cross-border regional “Tyrolean” identity; second, the perception that the EU’s debordering policies contributed significantly to rendering the border less visible; and the resulting opportunities for renewed or new cross-border interactions due to Schengen. Finally, the role of the EU in deconstructing borders has been frequently addressed by local politicians throughout the past decades and has thus been a key element in political discourse. While maintaining a strong local focus, the ‘Dolomiten’ emphasizes the role of the (open) border as a symbol of European integration and connects local concerns on re-bordering to the European dimension. Representatives of the German-speaking minority in South Tyrol highlight the significance of the local border crossing, the Brenner Pass, not only as a local border but also as a representation of what European states have achieved together. The newspaper thus presents a narrative of a Europe in crisis, portraying the threat of re-bordering as infringing upon shared EU fundamental principles. This narrative underscores the importance of the EU

and the associated de-bordering policies for the minority and the border region. It articulates the economic benefits of de-bordering, such as the preservation of cross-border flows and the free movement of EU citizens, as well as the political benefits, including peace, stability, and reconciliation. The narratives presented in the 'Dolomiten' thus hint towards a perception of the EU as a promoter of minorities and an arbitrator in conflicts.

EU-related narratives within minority newspapers predominantly depict the EU as an institution, policy-making organ and funding body, with limited emphasis on shared European heritage, beliefs or values and the idea of a community of Europeans. Instead, rebordering is predominantly framed in terms of free movement of goods, which suggests a common market-centered perspective, and a strong joint external border policy.

However, the EU's perceived responsibility regarding internal borders is less pronounced than expected, considering the EU's key role in overcoming state borders through the Schengen Agreement and cross-border policies. Minorities also strongly perceive the states, particularly kin states, as responsible for re-/and de-bordering policies. This further underscores a certain disconnect between the local and the European Union, with local concerns regarding rebordering processes not being framed as European concerns. Kin states are attributed particular responsibility and are often criticized for proceeding with border closures even though they should understand the special situation of minorities in borderlands, and their cross-border lifestyle. In the newspapers it is argued that kin states should adapt measures accordingly, highlighting a key cross-border dimension often overlooked in discussions on border policies.

The narratives on Europe in the minority newspapers analyzed portray the image of a rather distant EU. While cross-border connections are central to the lives of many minority members, these are primarily experienced as *trans-national* connection rather than European connections that go beyond states. Indeed, states continue to play a central role, with a particular emphasis on the kin state as central actor in shaping border policies.

5.3 Narrators Compared

In all case study regions, the most dominant voice featured in the newspapers is that of male politicians, followed by male economic actors. In contrast, the voices of civil society actors, and women in general, were rarely featured. There is also an absence of young voices in the newspapers analyzed.

The voices of individual migrants were absent. This is perhaps unsurprising given the hostile and threatening picture of migrants that was presented in the qualitative analysis. For example, both the Polish and Slovakian case studies we found articles that warned about the possible construction of refugee housing at the border, and the possible negative impact it would have on the national minority living in the area. However, the repercussions for the refugees themselves, who would be placed in these centers, was given little column space. Rather, this was presented as an issue for the national minority.

Overall, we find that the narratives regarding borders and Europe do not include diverse perspectives with a clear focus on the elites and major gender imbalance with a significant under-representation of female narrators. This probably reflects both the bias of media outlets in the selection of their sources, and the underrepresentation of women in the stakeholder categories cited by the newspapers (i.e. politicians, economic actors). This contributes to a rather one-dimensional picture within the media narratives and limited debate about the larger structures and symbolism of borders and little discussion of European identity and borders.

6. Conclusions

A key finding of our study is that the idea of closed or re-bordered borders often matters more in border narratives than the actual restrictions imposed around them. Indeed, the newspapers both talk more about plans of bordering, as well as the actual closing of state borders represent moments of tension for borderland minorities: they disrupt and impede relations to kin state and cross-border flows and lifestyles, whether it is in abstract or very concrete ways.

Moreover, although border areas are often considered as “laboratories” of European integration and minorities as more “European” than majority populations, there is a clear disconnect with Europe even in borderlands and among national minorities. The very local framing of borders across the case study regions signified that local issues are often not, or only loosely, connected to Europe and the European community. The findings suggest that just because the minority acts in a transnational space, this does not necessarily mean that minorities “think” in European terms, also with regards to their identity and values.

Yet, Europe – while distant from the borderlands - is not absent. Indeed, there is an intrinsic link between narratives on Europe and border narratives⁷ more broadly defined, even though this link can be quite weak as borders are perhaps more embedded in the local or the transnational than in the European dimension. Many of the narratives implicitly or explicitly refer to the European project, whether it is in reports about the EU as absent policymaker or for failing to implement a joint migration and border policy. Indeed, we cannot talk about borders without talking about Europe (including its absence or distance).

The aim of this report was to study narratives in minority media and to gather a macro-level perspective on border narratives before we engage in the qualitative part of Work Package 4. In the next phase of the research, we will use data gathered from this report in creative arts research activities with young adults living in borderland regions. Through this work we will contrast public and personal narratives. This will help the B-Shapes project to formulate a clearer picture of bottom up and personal, potentially novel, perspectives on borders and Europe in the case study regions, to understand and re-envision the idea of a socially and culturally coherent Europe and provide policy recommendations on how to create a more resilient, inclusive, and democratic European society.

⁷ As explored in B-Shapes Deliverable D2.1

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